

Microballoons In Medicine: A Buoyant Breakthrough In Reshaping Diabetes Therapy

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus, a chronic condition characterized by persistent hyperglycemia caused by inadequate insulin secretion or activity, affects millions of individuals worldwide. Reduced bioavailability, shorter half-lives, and quick gastrointestinal transit are common limitations of conventional oral antidiabetic treatments, which lead to less-than-ideal glucose control and worse patient compliance. The use of gastro retentive drug delivery systems, especially microballoons, has become a viable way to get around these restrictions. Microballoons are hollow, low-density, polymer-based microspheres designed to float on the gastric fluid, thereby prolonging gastrointestinal residence time and enabling controlled or sustained release of encapsulated drugs. This buoyant property ensures extended contact time of drug with the absorptive regions of the upper GI tract, enhancing bioavailability and maintaining uniform plasma drug concentrations. Recent formulation advancements, including the use of binary solvent systems, polymeric composites, and mucoadhesive modifications, have further improved the structural integrity, buoyancy, and release kinetics of microballoons loaded with antidiabetic agents such as metformin, glipizide, glimepiride, and repaglinide. Moreover, emerging research explores the potential of microballoons for multidrug delivery, combining agents with complementary mechanisms to optimize glycemic management while reducing dosing frequency. Despite most developments being at the preclinical stage, rational design frameworks, systematic optimization, and novel polymer technologies provide a solid foundation for clinical translation. Overall, microballoons represent a versatile and innovative platform, offering improved therapeutic efficacy, patient compliance, and safety in the oral management of diabetes mellitus, signaling a buoyant breakthrough in drug delivery and disease management.

Keywords: Microballoons, Gastroretentive drug delivery system, Buoyancy, Diabetes, Bioavailability.

INTRODUCTION

A prevalent endocrine condition is diabetes mellitus (DM). The prevalence of diabetes is currently rising quickly throughout the world.¹ It is typified by insulin resistance, which is frequently accompanied by different levels of insulin secretion abnormalities. Ultimately, this condition results in decreased insulin release from the pancreatic beta cells.² Diabetes mellitus is classified into two types, which includes type 1 DM and type 2 DM. Autoimmune β -cell death is the main cause for type 1 diabetes, which typically leads to total insulin insufficiency and perhaps autoimmune diabetes mellitus in maturity. Type 2

diabetes mellitus is accompanied by progressive reduction in β -cell insulin production and insulin resistance.^{3,4} Report from international diabetes federation showed that 589 million people suffered from the diabetes in 2024. By 2045, this figure is may rise to 783.2 million.⁵ Diabetes-related complications, which have a substantial impact on the morbidity and death of individuals, have increased in tandem with the disease's rising incidence. Prevention of the disorder complications, lowering death rate, maintaining a standard quality of life by preventing the acute decompensation are the key objectives in the management of diabetes mellitus.⁶

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

The dosage forms which can be retained in the stomach for long periods of the time. Hence, the name gastroretentive drug delivery systems.^{7,8} These systems were created as a result of traditional methods incapacity to hold drugs in the gastric region. In the upper GI tract, GRDDS induces site-specific release of medication for either local or systemic effects.⁹ The ability of these systems to reside in the gastric region for longer period of time greatly prolongs the drug retention and enhances bioavailability.¹⁰ Gastric retention can be achieved through various approaches such as effervescent approach and non-effervescent approach.¹¹ Non-effervescent approach includes magnetic system, high-density system, super porous hydrogels, low-density systems, expandable systems, and mucoadhesive or bio-adhesive systems.^{12,13}

MICROBALLOONS

Microballoons has emerged as a promising gastro retentive drug-delivery systems which comes under non-effervescent systems. Microballoons, sometimes referred to as hollow microspheres, are essentially spherical, core-free particles.¹⁴ These microspheres, which are free-flowing powders composed of protein or combination of polymers, are typically smaller than 200 micrometers.¹⁵ These are regarded as some of the best systems having buoyancy with the unique benefits of multiple unit systems and superior floating properties.¹⁶

The various fabrication techniques for the microballoon preparation include, emulsion solvent evaporation technique, solvent diffusion technique, spray drying and spray congealing, ionotropic gelation technique, phase separation and coacervation techniques.¹⁷ These are designed to be sufficiently buoyant to afloat on top of stomach contents and remain there for an extended period of time.¹⁸ This characteristic increases stomach retention and lessens the need for repeated dosing by facilitating the gradual release of medications at the intended rate. Consequently, medications with short half-lives can have a more potent therapeutic effect. Additionally, this prolonged gastric retention brought on by buoyancy improves the absorption of medications that dissolve in the stomach.¹⁹ The drug's enhanced floating properties and delayed release at the ideal rate are mostly due to the concentration of

polymers and solvents utilized in the formulation. The preferred polymers for microballoons are ethyl cellulose, hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose and Eudragit R S-100.²⁰

MECHANISM OF MICROBALLOONS

Microballoons due to their lower density and sufficient buoyancy, they can float above GI fluid and reside in the gastric region for longer time. As the dosage form floats above the stomach fluid, the medication is administered gradually in a controlled manner, improving retention time and reducing differences in plasma drug concentration. The formed colloidal gel barrier delays entering fluid into the dosage causing the gel to form and the polymer layer to hydrate. Because the inflated polymer retains air, the microballoons are buoyant and have a lower density than stomach fluid. However, it is crucial to remember that effective fulfillment of buoyancy only requires a minimal amount of stomach material. In both fed and fasted stages, adhesion of the medication to the wall of the gastric region is possible which provides mucoadhesive properties of the particles that have not been impacted by the stomach contents especially non-adherent mucus.^{21,22} Acrylic resin hollow microspheres, Ethyl cellulose, eudragit, polyethylene oxide, polycarbonate floating balloons, polystyrene floatable shells, gelucire containing floating granules, hypromellose are the examples of recent innovations. Micro balloons gel forming agents regulates the rate at which fluid enters the dosage form, this barrier controls the release of medication. The hydration of the neighbouring hydrocolloid layer keeps the formed gel layer intact when the microballoon's exterior dissolves. The air trapped in the inflated polymer becomes more buoyant and loses density as a result of this hydration.^{23,24}

FABRICATION OF MICROBALLOONS

POLYMERS

Polymers like ethyl cellulose(EC), hydroxy propyl cellulose, cellulose acetate, hydroxy-propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC), cellulose acetate butyrate, eudragit, polylactic acid, polylactic co glycolic acid, polycaprolactone, polystyrene, cellulose acetate phthalate(CAP), chitosan, acrycoat, Carbopol,

methocil are used in the formulation of microballoons.

Ethyl Cellulose

Over the past 50-60 years, polymer ethyl cellulose has been used widely. It is derived from cellulose where some hydroxyl groups on the repeating anhydroglucose units will be modified into ethyl ether groups, largely called as non-ionic ethyl ether of cellulose. It is frequently used in pharmaceutical formulations for a number of purposes, including as stabilizing, disguising the taste of bitter drugs, retaining moisture, and functioning as an extended-release binder in inert matrix systems. As the molecular weight of EC increases, drug release rates are significantly decreased. When combined with specific plasticizing agents, it can be utilized as a matrix forming agent.²⁵

Eudragit RS

Eudragit RS 100 is a widely used synthetic polymer belonging to the family of methacrylate copolymers, extensively employed in controlled and sustained drug delivery systems. It is especially useful in the formulation of floating microspheres, microballoons, matrix tablets, and coated dosage forms. Eudragit RS100 is a white powder that is solid and has a subtle, distinctive smell. At pH 5 or lower, it dissolves in gastric fluid. Eudragit RS 100 forms the structural matrix of microballoons. When processed (e.g., solvent evaporation, emulsion solvent diffusion), it solidifies into hollow spheres with a gas-filled core.^{26,27}

Hydroxy- Propyl Methyl Cellulose

Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose is a white/ off-white, odorless, water-soluble polymer that can be used for binding, thickening, holding water, forming films, and as a lubricant. It is a semi synthetic, chemically inert, viscoelastic polymer used for controlled-delivery of drugs in several commercial products and oral medications. Eudragit polymethacrylates are primarily employed as film coating materials in tablet formulations. The kind of polymers used can produce films with different solubility characteristics.²⁸

SOLVENTS

Solvents having good volatile nature are used which is essential for creating the hollow internal cavity and low-density structure and also it should separate from the emulsion with ease, leaving behind hollow microspheres. Various solvents include DCM, chloroform, acetone, ethyl acetate, dimethylformamide, dimethyl sulfoxide. Single solvent system in the fabrication of microballoons are less common because they form irregular microballoons. Hence, ratios of solvents are used for enhancing the stability of the formulation. e.g., Dichloromethane: ethanol, chloroform: methanol, Ethyl acetate: ethanol, ethyl acetate: acetone, DCM: acetone. Cosolvents such as ethanol, methanol and isopropyl alcohol was used, volatile solvent and cosolvent in the ratio of 1:1 or 3:1.

Dichloromethane: Ethanol

Dichloromethane also known as methylene chloride. This organic solvent has been widely employed in synthesis. DCM is the most widely used solvent in the fabrication of microballoons due its high volatility. It helps in dissolving the hydrophobic polymers such as ethyl cellulose and eudragit. DCM alone may form ruptured or collapsed and irregular microballoons. Hence, DCM is employed with ethanol in the ratio of 1:1 or 2:1. since ethanol acts as a cosolvent, it helps in solubilizing the drugs and polymers which are not completely soluble with DCM alone. The specific ratios of DCM and ethanol help in the formation of smooth spherical microballoons.²⁹

Chloroform: Methanol

Chloroform is a volatile organic solvent that has been used in the formulation of microballoons. It helps in dissolving the hydrophobic polymers and forms uniform polymer drug solution responsible for forming microballoons. Chloroform alone may cause premature polymer precipitation leads to collapsed microballoons due to the rapid evaporation of the solvent. Hence, chloroform is employed with methanol in the ratio of 1:1, 2:1. Methanol acts as a cosolvent which helps in balancing the polymer solubility, solvent evaporation and formation of hollow cavity. The ratio of chloroform and methanol helps in obtaining the microballoons with desired

floating behavior and desired morphology. But this solvent system in the formulation is less used due to its toxicity.³⁰

Ethyl acetate: Ethanol

Ethyl acetate is a sweet-smelling, colorless liquid. Ethyl acetate and other solvents are frequently combined for synthesis in laboratories. Ethyl acetate is a safe solvent which helps in dissolving the polymer and formation of the cavity. It has moderate volatility and partial water miscibility. Ethyl acetate alone has limited drug solubility and incomplete hollow cavity formation. Hence, ethyl acetate is employed with ethanol in the ratio of 1:1, 3:1. Ethanol acts as a cosolvent and helps in formation of the efficient hollow cavity. The ratio of ethyl acetate and ethanol helps in formation of the stable buoyant microballoons with enhanced drug entrapment and controlled release.³¹

TECHNIQUES FOR FABRICATION OF MICROBALLOONS

Emulsion Solvent Evaporation Method

In this method, the appropriate amount of polymer is weighed and dissolved in organic solvent, followed by incorporation of the drug into the same. For oil in water emulsion, the drug containing solution is added to an aqueous phase, thereby formation of emulsion occurs. Once a stable emulsion has formed, the oil in water emulsion is stirred vigorously by increasing temperature to allow the evaporation of organic solvent. This removal of solvent results in polymer precipitation at the water or oil interface of droplets, creating a cavity which gives the floating behaviour to them. Eudragit RS, ethyl cellulose and HPMC and many excipients are used in the creation of such systems.³² For creating the homogenous solutions, excipients were combined with medications, dissolved in volatile solutions like acetone, dichloromethane etc. either alone or in specific ratio. The final mixture was added to hundred milliliters of aqueous solution that is spinning at 1500 RPM. After creation of emulsion, it is heated for three more hours at 35 °C as shown in fig 1. The acetone or dichloromethane is totally evaporated once a stable emulsion has formed, and the hardened microballoons undergo filtering using Whatman filter paper. The

floating and prolonged qualities are imparted by these hollow microballoons.^{33,34}

Fig 1: Emulsion Solvent Evaporation Method for Preparation of Microballoons

Emulsion Solvent Diffusion Technique

The drug and an organic solvent have a better affinity in the solvent diffusion technique than in solvent evaporation technique. Despite the miscibility of organic solution, the drug dissolves and the resulting solution mixture disperses in water based solution to produce droplets of emulsion.³⁵ The drug crystallizes through the slow diffusion of the organic solvent from the droplets into the adjacent aqueous solution into droplets as shown in fig 2. The mixture of drug and polymer is added as drops to polyvinyl alcohol solution after being solubilized in ratio of ethanol and dichloromethane. This mixture is agitated at various temperatures for one hour at 1500 rpm. Microballoons with different medication concentrations can be made by varying the polymer concentration in cosolvents and ethanol to dichloromethane ratio.^{36,37}

Fig 2: Emulsion-solvent diffusion technique for the preparation of microballoons

Solvent Diffusion Evaporation Technique

This process differs slightly from both emulsion solvent diffusion method and the emulsion solvent evaporation method. This is based on the diffusion of a volatile organic solvent from polymer droplets into an external phase, followed by evaporating the

solvent, which leads to polymer precipitation at the droplet surface.³⁸ The excipients is dissolved in an organic solution to obtain a homogeneous mixture, then the right amount of drug is dissolved or dispersed into the polymer containing solution under continuous stirring, then this drug polymer solution is slowly introduced into the external phase under constant mechanical stirring, which results in the emulsion creation. After formation of emulsion, the solvent with high affinity diffuses out rapidly from emulsion droplets. Continue stirring until the remaining solvent evaporates completely. As the solvent evaporates the polymer precipitates and forms a rigid outer shell which results in the formation of microballoons as shown in fig 3. The microballoons which are formed were collected and washed repeatedly using suitable solvent to remove adhered oil. The microballoons are dried at a room temperature or under vacuum to get a free-flowing powder.^{39,40}

Fig 3: Solvent diffusion evaporation technique for the preparation of microballoons

Iontropic Gelation Method

The ionotropic or ionic gelation method will be based on the electrostatic interaction between oppositely charged polymers and multivalent ions, leading to the formation of a cross-linked polymeric matrix. In this method, polymers such as pectin, chitosan, sodium alginate undergo gelation in the presence of cross-linking agents like calcium chloride or sodium tripolyphosphate. The formation of microballoons occurs due to simultaneous gelation and entrapment of air or gas, producing hollow, low-density, floating particles.⁴¹ To prepare microballoons, a polymer solution was prepared by accurately weighing sodium alginate and dissolved in appropriate quantity of water, then the drug was added into the polymer solution. In another beaker, cross linking agent such as right amount of calcium chloride was dissolved in water under gentle stirring and the polymer solution

containing drug was added dropwise using a syringe into Ca^{2+} solution as shown in fig 4. On contact with calcium ions, instantaneous ionic cross-linking of alginate occurs, forming spherical gelled microballoons. The formed microballoons were kept in cross linking solution for a specified period of time to ensure complete internal gelation. The solution was then filtered, washed repeatedly using distilled water for removing the drug residing on the surface and resultant microballoons were collected and dried using oven drying, air drying, lyophilization.^{42,43}

Fig 4: Iontropic gelation technique for the preparation of microballoons

Coacervation and Phase Separation Method

Coacervation and phase separation is a microencapsulation technique in which a polymer separates out from a solution and forms a polymer-rich coating around a drug. This technique is in accordance with the decrease in polymer solubility in the phase that is organic, which produces coacervation, a phase rich in polymers. To prepare microballoons by this method, the appropriate amount of the polymer dissolves in an appropriate organic solvent to obtain a clear and homogeneous polymer solution. Then the known amount of drug was dispersed or dissolved in the solution containing polymer under gentle stirring. As shown in fig 5, the drug polymer solution is slowly introduced into the non-miscible liquid phase under constant mechanical stirring which forms oil in oil emulsion. The phase-separation is induced by slow solvent evaporation or addition of a non-solvent. As the solvent diffuses out, the polymer separates from the solution and forms a polymer rich coacervate phase. Addition of hardening agent such as n hexane helps in solidifying the polymer shell. The formed microballoons will be collected, filtered and washed thoroughly for

removing residual oil, followed by drying at ambient room temperature or under vacuum to get a free-flowing powder.⁴⁴

Fig 5: Coacervation and phase separation method for preparation of microballoons

Spray Drying and Spray Congealing Method

In spray drying, the coating is solidified by quickly evaporating the solvent that dissolves the coating ingredient. For drying and forming particles, spray drying is the most popular industrial method. The necessary bulk density, particle shape, and particle size distribution may all be achieved in a single step using this method. Spray congealing involves solidification of molten mixture of drug and carrier when it is atomized into a chamber containing a cool air or gas.⁴⁵ Firstly, to create a slurry, the excipients were dissolved in a suitable volatile organic solution like dichloromethane, acetone. The slurry is sprayed into the drying chamber as shown in fig 5, concentration gradient develops inside the smaller droplets with higher concentration at the surface of droplet. Its because of time taken for the solute to diffuse is greater than the solution in the droplets to evaporate while drying process. Therefore, a solid shell forms leads to the creation of hollow microspheres. A cyclone separator is often used for separating the solid product from the gas, remove any remaining solvent through vacuum drying, and store the goods for future use.⁴⁶

Fig 6: Spray drying and spray congealing method for the preparation of microballoons

ANTIDIABETIC DRUG-SPECIFIC UTILIZATION OF MICROBALLOONS

Solvent Evaporation Technique for Glimepiride and Repaglinide Microballoons

As shown in table 1, the solvent evaporation technique is highly utilized for formulating glimepiride, and repaglinide encapsulated microballoons. This method is highly suitable because of its effectiveness in encapsulating poorly water-soluble drugs. The drugs glimepiride and repaglinide comes under BCS class II which shows poor water solubility. These drugs have short half-life and absorption site is upper GI tract. Studies have reported that microballoons prepared by this method has shown good buoyancy, high entrapment efficiency and sustained release profiles. The glimepiride has shown high entrapment efficiency whereas repaglinide has shown good sustained release profile and extended retention of the drug in stomach which highlights the adaptability of this technique. Since these drugs are antidiabetic agents, these formulation strategies are particularly useful in the management of diabetes mellitus by improving the bioavailability and enhanced glycaemic control.^{47,48,49}

Emulsion Solvent Diffusion Method for Glipizide Microballoons

Emulsion solvent diffusion technique is employed for microballoons loaded with glipizide drug as shown in table 1. In reported studies, glipizide is dissolved or dispersed with suitable solvents and polymers to formulate it into microballoons. Glipizide is BCS class II which has poor water solubility, short half-life and the absorption site for glipizide is upper GI tract. The glipizide loaded microballoons formulated by this method have shown good floating behaviour, satisfactory drug entrapment and sustained release behaviour. Glipizide belongs to second generation sulfonylurea class which helps in the management of diabetes by enhancing the bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy.⁵⁰

Emulsion Solvent Evaporation Technique for Metformin Microballoons

The conventional solvent evaporation technique involves the direct evaporation of a volatile organic

solvent from a polymer–drug solution, the emulsion solvent evaporation method incorporates an initial emulsification step of the organic phase into an aqueous medium. This modification allows better control of particle size, uniformity, and buoyancy, making it particularly suitable for drugs belong to BCS class II. As shown in table 1 the drug metformin was prepared by emulsion evaporation technique which is formulated into microballoons to obtain enhanced floatability. Metformin is a biguanide antihyperglycemic agent with high aqueous solubility and short half-life. It is absorbed primarily in upper gastrointestinal tract.⁵¹ Metformin belongs to BCS class III, its highest solubility and short half-life set drawback of maintaining sustained plasma levels through conventional oral dosage forms. Hence, by formulating it into microballoons enhances the time of residence for the drug in stomach region, allows controlled release and improves bioavailability.^{52,53}

Ionotropic Gelation Technique for Repaglinide Microballoons

As shown in table 1, ionotropic gelation method is particularly suitable for repaglinide microballoons due to its mild conditions, solvent-free nature, and ability to produce biodegradable, floating microspheres with sustained release. Repaglinide is a meglitinide derivative which are BCS class II have low water miscibility and short half-life. Its absorption site is upper GIT. Repaglinide loaded microballoons formulated by this method allows formation of floating, biodegradable microballoons capable of prolonged gastric retention and controlled release.⁵⁴

Table 1: Antidiabetic Drug-Specific Utilization of Microballoons

Drug	Method used for preparation
Glimepiride	Solvent Evaporation Method
Repaglinide	Solvent Evaporation Method
Glipizide	Emulsion Solvent Diffusion Method
Metformin	Emulsion Solvent Evaporation Method
Repaglinide	Ionotropic Gelation Method

MICROBALLOONS-MARKETED FORMULATIONS⁵⁵

Table 2: List of Commercial Microballoon Formulations

Drug	Brand names	Manufacturer names
Propranolol HCl	Inderal	Pellets pharma LTD
Theophylline	Uniphyl	Kores India LTD
Domperidone	Motilium	Nishchem International P.V.T LTD
Nizatidine	Tazac	Dr. Reddy's Laboratory LTD

APPLICATIONS OF MICROBALLOONS IN DIABETES MANAGEMENT

Gastroretentive Oral Delivery of Antidiabetic Agents: Conventional oral dosage forms often pass rapidly through gastric regions, resulting in incomplete absorption and reduced therapeutic efficacy. Many antidiabetic agents, such as metformin, repaglinide, glipizide, and glimepiride, exhibit optimal absorption in the stomach. These drugs have shorter half-life and lesser bioavailability. Hence, formulating these drugs into hollow microspheres retains the drug in gastric region for a long time which helps in the management of diabetes mellitus.⁵⁶

Controlled or Sustained Release of Drugs: Microballoon provides controlled or sustained release of the antidiabetic drugs. The polymeric shell surrounding the hollow core regulates drug diffusion and erosion, enabling prolonged drug release over several hours results in gradual release of the drugs into bloodstream which helps in maintaining the uniform plasma drug concentration which in turn results in stable glucose levels in the body helps in managing diabetes mellitus more effectively by reducing the frequency of dosing.^{56,57}

Improved Absorption and Bioavailability: Poor absorption and bioavailability remain as significant disadvantages in oral therapy with antidiabetic drugs. In order to overcome these limitations microballoon based systems were used by encapsulating antidiabetic drugs. Microballoons enhance bioavailability of antidiabetic agents by prolonging the gastric retention with controlled drug release.

Extended contact time between the drug and the absorptive surfaces of the upper gastrointestinal tract allows more efficient absorption before the drug undergoes degradation or metabolism. Hence, the diabetes can be managed effectively by overcoming the limitations of conventional oral therapy of antidiabetic agents.^{57,58}

Reduced Gastrointestinal Adverse Effects:

Gastrointestinal side effects, such as nausea, abdominal discomfort, and diarrhoea, are commonly associated with conventional oral antidiabetic therapy, especially with drugs like metformin. Rapid drug release and high local drug concentration in the gastrointestinal tract are key contributors to these side effects. Microballoons, by providing gradual and sustained drug release, reduce sudden exposure of the gastrointestinal mucosa to high drug concentrations. This controlled exposure may help lower the incidence and severity of gastrointestinal irritation, thereby improving patient tolerance and adherence to therapy.⁵⁸

Potential for Multidrug Delivery: Microballoons, owing to their hollow structure and polymeric matrix, can be engineered to encapsulate more than one drug either within the same carrier or as separate populations of microballoons combined into a single dosage form. This flexibility allows the delivery of drugs with different physicochemical properties and pharmacokinetic profiles. By modifying polymer composition, shell thickness, and drug distribution, microballoons can be designed to achieve simultaneous or sequential release of multiple antidiabetic agents which provides better glycaemic control.⁵⁹

RECENT ADVANCEMENTS IN THE FORMULATION OF MICROBALLOON WITH ANTIDIABETIC AGENTS

In recent years a considerable progress was made in the denovo design of microballoons as gastroretentive drug-delivery system for delivering the antidiabetic agents. These advancements have been made to prevail over the disadvantages of conventional dosage forms such as low solubility, poor bioavailability and side effects associated with frequent dosing. Based on the literature survey, the researchers using novel polymer combinations, improved formulation

strategies to enhance the drug entrapment efficiency, gastric retention and controlled release profiles.

Novel Polymer Systems: The recent studies showing that the researchers are using advanced polymer systems to modify the drug release profile and to achieve good morphology of microballoons with high entrapment efficiency. Polymers such as ethyl cellulose, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose(HPMC), and grades of eudragit RS are of major significance in the formulation of microballoons. The researchers have achieved good entrapment efficiency, stability of microballoons for antidiabetic agents like metformin, glipizide and repaglinide. Optimized polymer ratios have resulted in robust performance with high entrapment efficiency, improved bioavailability and good sustained release properties with better glycemic control.⁶⁰

Ratio of Solvent Systems: Based on the literature survey the common solvents employed in the formulation include dichloromethane, chloroform, ethyl acetate. Single solvent systems have resulted in the formation of irregular and collapsed microballoons. Hence, the researchers are combining two solvents in a specific ratio to overcome the limitations of microballoon formulation. The use of solvents and cosolvents in a specific ratio have resulted in the formation of smooth spherical microablloons without causing any rupture.⁶⁰

Quality By Design And Process Optimization:

Quality by design principles is increasingly applied by the researchers in microballoon formulation. These principles help in the identification of critical process parameters which affects size, shape of the particles, buoyancy, release kinetics and entrapment efficiency. The parameters which affect the final formulation is stirring speed, temperature, solvent ratio, drug polymer ratio, solvent type, solvent and polymer concentration. By modifying these parameters accordingly helps in formation of stable, buoyant microablloons with improved glycemic control.⁶¹

Integration of Mucoadhesive Components: To further prolong retention at the gastric mucosa and improve absorption, mucoadhesive polymers such as chitosan and alginate are being combined with microballoon systems. While much of the mucoadhesive research comes from related

microsphere studies, these bioadhesive modifications show potential for future microballoon formulations of antidiabetic drugs by enhancing contact time at the absorption site, thereby increasing therapeutic efficacy and possibly reducing dosing frequency.⁶²

Scaling and Translational Challenges: Many advancements in the denovo design of microballoons remain at the preclinical or developmental stage, there is a growing emphasis on addressing the formulation challenges and manufacturing requirements. Implementation of design strategies, frameworks and novel polymer systems lays a foundation for a stable gastroretentive microballoon systems into clinically viable products for managing diabetes mellitus.⁶³

CONCLUSION

A novel and promising gastro-retentive drug delivery method is microballoons. For antidiabetic drugs with limited absorption windows or short biological half-lives, their special hollow structure, low density, and extended stomach residence time allow for sustained release and enhanced bioavailability. Microballoons help to achieve consistent plasma concentrations, eliminate volatility associated with conventional therapy, and reduce dosage frequency by keeping medications in upper GI tract for extended or longer time period. In order to increase the time of residence of antidiabetic medications and increase the therapeutic efficacy, the review discusses some of the most recent research that employs state-of-the-art techniques for creating conventional or modified microballoons. The customizable release patterns that are suited to the pharmacokinetic requirements of different antidiabetic medications are further made possible by the use of polymers like Eudragit, HPMC, and ethyl cellulose. All things considered, microballoons present a fresh and practical approach to reducing diabetes, with great potential to revolutionize the delivery of oral antidiabetic medications and improve disease control.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the Principal and Management of CMR College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, for their continuous encouragement and valuable support.

Conflict of interest (If any)

No conflict of interest

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HOW TO CITE: V. T. Iswariya, Pavuja M. V*, V. Uma Maheswara Rao, Microballoons in Medicine: A Buoyant Breakthrough In Reshaping Diabetes Therapy J. Pharm. Sci., 2026, 2 (2), 207--218. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18613523>

